

Effect of Physical Environment Quality on the Customer Loyalty through Perceived Value and Customer Satisfaction in De Soematra 1910 Restaurant in Surabaya

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Abstract

This paper main aim is to maintain and improve restaurant performance becomes more competitive and seeks to improve customer loyalty for De Soematra 1910 restaurant in Surabaya and an interesting research model that can be applied to the De Soematra 1910 restaurant as an object in Surabaya which has an exclusive colonial style design (Dutch era) and has a unique vibes. A quantitative with data processing using AMOS. Data collection was carried out by distributing questionnaires to 250 respondents with the characteristics of male and female in the age range 18-60 years, have visited and had done fine dining at least 2 times in the last 6 months and monthly income between IDR 1,000,000,- IDR 20,000,000,, at the De Soematra 1910 in Surabaya. The results showed that 9 hypotheses were accepted and 10 hypotheses were rejected. The paper also statistically shows significant and insignificant relationships between 7 dimensions of Physical Environment Quality (Aesthetics, Ambience, Lighting, Table Settings, Layout, Staff and Music) that affect Customer Loyalty through the dimensions of Perceived Value (Hedonic and Utilitarian) and Customer Satisfaction. The research findings present incremental implications for De Soematra 1910 restaurant marketing management. Findings recommend that manager, service providers – procedures and Physical Environment Quality elements would make service quality standards becomes high level preferred by the customers toward first class restaurant. This should subsequently helps the restaurant building their strong satisfaction, loyalty and positive image.

Keywords: Physical Environment Quality, Perceived Value, Hedonic, Utilitarian, Customer Satisfaction, Customer Loyalty.

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1.1 Introduction

Indonesia in the fourth quarter of 2018 with a total population of about 265 million inhabitants. This increase is dominated by middle and upper class population so that population density is driving growth in the food and beverage industry sector, one of which is due to increased income of the community and the growth of the upper middle class and upper class or currently called the rich community (BPS - Statistic Indonesia, 2018). The growth of the middle class and above is based on data from the Indonesian Central Statistics Agency that the average income of Indonesians has increased by around 7.92% from IDR 51.89 million in 2017 to IDR 56 million per year. With this amount of income, Indonesia meets the World Bank category in the middle to upper income group (CNN Indonesia, 2019). The growth of upper class society has increased based on the 2019 World Wealth Report where the calculation of wealth data worldwide uses processed data in 2018. Individuals with high wealth are called high-net-worth-individuals (HNWI) in Indonesia through the top 25 in the population list of people the richest reached 129 thousand people in 2018 increased from 2017. This shows the number of richest people in Indonesia is also the highest in Southeast Asia as the only one who penetrated the top 25 are ranked 23rd in the world. (Liputan6 News, 2019). The latest report states that an estimated 85.4% (145.41 million people) of the adult population in Indonesia have a wealth of under US \$ 10,000 or IDR 150 million in the exchange rate of IDR 15,000 / US \$ United States (US). Then the next data is, 13.7% (23.32 million people) have a wealth of between US \$ 10,000-100,000, then 0.8% (1.39 million people) has a wealth of US \$ 100,000-1,000,000 and 0.1 % (89 thousand people) with a wealth of more than US \$ 1 million. This supports the growth of public opinion in Indonesia along with the times. (katadata, 2018). As for the food and beverage industry sector to encourage economic growth throughout 2018, the food and beverage industry will grow by 7.91% or surpass the national economic growth of 5.17% (Kementerian Perindustrian Republik Indonesia, 2019). Along with economic growth in Indonesia, in second quarter of 2017 that the food and beverage industry is included in the manufacturing industry as the highest sector with a contribution of 20.26% which is superior than other sectors (Kementerian Perindustrian Indonesia, 2017).

Based on data from the Central Statistics Agency on the growth of HOREKA (Hotels, Restaurants and Cafes) in Indonesia has increased every year from 2009 to 2016. The rise of culinary tourism in recent years, also helped encourage the growth of food service providers and drinks. Especially restaurants or cafes where as a type of service business or the provision of food and beverages located in some or all permanent buildings by selling and serving food and drinks to the general public. The increase in the last 3 years in the restaurant and cafe business activities showed a significant increase from 2014 of 4,291 businesses, a further increase of 644 businesses to 4,935 businesses and a drastic increase of 740 businesses to 5,675 businesses (BPS - Statistic Indonesia, 2016). In fine dining restaurants, the target segment is usually upper class or upper middle class people and they pay not only for the service but also for prestige, luxury and status related to the customer's self (Nupur et al., 2017). De Soematra 1910 restaurant in Surabaya is one of the restaurants that has a segment of middle to upper class and upper class customers established in 1910 in Surabaya. At the end of 2012, De Soematra 1910 Restaurant in Surabaya was chosen as one of the Cultural Heritage as a "Cultural Heritage" in Surabaya, East Java (De Soematra 1910, 2019). Achieved the title as a heritage of "Cultural Heritage" because this can be proven when entering De Soematra 1910 Restaurant in Surabaya, customers are welcomed with an identical atmosphere of luxury Dutch era, this exclusive and elegant 5-star service sets it

apart from other places or multipurpose spaces. Customers can enjoy the lounge and private dining area as well as 2 multipurpose spaces located outdoors in the garden. Equipped with internet, international standard services, live music and trained staff who can help plan and organize events. In addition, it is supported by various Italian, European, Fusion, and Indonesian menu choices (De Soematra 1910, 2019). De Soematra 1910 Restaurant in Surabaya is one of the luxurious dining places located on Jalan Sumatra No. 75 - Surabaya, several well-known eating places also open here. On the same street there are restaurants Domicile Kitchen & Lounge and Isola, 2 places that are no less famous. In contrast to the 2 restaurants, De Soematra serves a fine dining menu and therefore a competitor worthy of De Soematra 1910 Restaurant in Surabaya is a Tutto Bono restaurant that serves Italian and European menus and has a very warm atmosphere with an excellent layout and many choices of places sit according to the customer's wishes. (IDN Times, 2018).

In Surabaya, one of the restaurants that became the second competitor is Angus House which is an upscale dining area that provides a luxurious dining experience. Angus House with its flagship charcoal steak grill is familiar in the ears of meat lovers, the classic monochrome interior gives a touch of luxury and facets of food using a broth-based sauce and all steaks are served on sizzling hot plates. In addition to steaks like Kobe beef, Wagyu rib eye beef and Angus House-style spaghetti menu with more than 20 types of variants (Traveloka, 2017). This research was conducted based on the research gap, the first research gap is the effect of physical environment quality on perceived value. The results of Özdemir and Dinçer (2018) show a significant relationship between physical environment quality and perceived value. Ryu et al. (2012) did not show a significant relationship between physical environment quality and perceived value so that further research needs to be done to address the existing research gaps. The second research gap is the effect of physical environment quality on perceived value. The results of the study by Liu and Jang (2009) found that there was a significant and no significant effect on the dimensions of physical environment quality where aesthetics (interior design) and staff factors had a significant effect on perceived value, while ambience and layout had no significant effect on perceived value. This is because restaurant customers pay more attention to tangible service quality attributes (tangible) such as interior design and human elements who are restaurant staff. The findings of this study indicate that customer value perceptions may depend more on intangible aspects than intangible aspects.

This research is important because developments in the food and beverage sector in East Java have increased with the emergence of fine dining restaurants over the years. This makes De Soematra 1910 restaurant in Surabaya have new competitors that have sprung up such as Tutto Bono, Angus House and others so that it is necessary to maintain and improve this good performance to be more competitive and seek how to increase customer loyalty towards De Soematra 1910 restaurant customers in Surabaya. Secondly, this research is important because the research model used is an interesting research model that can be applied to the De Soematra 1910 restaurant object in Surabaya which has an exclusive colonial style design in the Dutch era and has a different atmosphere from other restaurants. This study focuses on customers who have visited and done fine dining at least 2 times in the last 6 months to become more interesting to be discussed in greater detail in terms of their influence and relationship in each of these factors whether it can create customer loyalty to customers.

2.1 Literature Review

2.1.1 Customer Loyalty

Customer loyalty is an ongoing commitment and affective commitment, both of which reflect the customer's intention to maintain relationships with certain products or services from the elements of the restaurant and also the psychological side, such as his love of a product and service of a restaurant (Garnefeld et al., 2011). This is supported by Han and Ryu (2009) suggesting that Customer loyalty occurs through the Physical Environment Quality of restaurants, Perceived Value and Customer Satisfaction while Weiss et al. (2004) argue that environmental and atmospheric quality and customer perceptions influence satisfaction and satisfaction influences the tendency to re-visit restaurants. Loyal customers have higher commitment and stronger emotional ties with restaurants (Gounaris and Stathakopoulos, 2004). Yoo and Bai (2013) emphasize that loyal customers feel they only know and become less interested in competing restaurant marketing strategies. (Chang, 2000), Customer Loyalty was found to be influenced by Physical Environment Quality indirectly influencing mediated through Customer Satisfaction. Customers who have the intention to repurchase and recommend to others have a higher chance to remain loyal to the restaurant (Kandampully and Suhartanto, 2000).

2.1.2 Customer Satisfaction

According to Schiffman et al. (2010), Customer Satisfaction is an individual customer satisfaction based on service and product performance that has a relationship with customer expectations while at the restaurant. Feelings of pleasure or disappointment of customers that arise after comparing between perceptions and an impression he gets on the performance and results of a service and expectations where the response of customers who feel satisfied after making a specific purchase of this service depends on the performance of services offered in connection with customer expectations. Expectations from customers are influenced by previous customer transaction experience, recommendations of friends, family and colleagues as well as information from restaurant marketers (Kotler, 2007). Customer satisfaction is one of the important goals for every restaurant business in order to build long-term relationships with customers as a top priority. Customer relationship is a core process in service so the process of making customers feel satisfied reflects the key to success. (Zameer et al., 2015).

2.1.3 Perceived Value

Perceived Value is the value that is felt by the customer as a whole for services based on perceptions related to whatever is received and given accordingly (Zeithaml, 1988). Perceived Value is everything that a customer expects from a product or service that is influenced by various factors such as risk, price, quality, benefits and sacrifice. However, businesses have recently become interested in the Hedonic and Utilitarian aspects of the values felt by Nejati and Moghaddam (2013).

2.1.3.1 Utilitarian

Utilitarians are customer-oriented and there is an urge from individuals to choose products and services efficiently based on rational reasons such as the value of efficiency and achievement (Anderson et al., 2012). Utilitarian value of a service concerns proper performance (Ramazanali, 2010). Two dimensions of Utilitarian perception value are the ratio of benefits in terms of efficiency and achievement, efficiency means the customer does not sacrifice time and sacrifices anything else for nothing, feels loss or is not useful and

achievement means that the customer has come to the restaurant is considered successful in terms of service and product quality. according to customer plans and expectations (Kim, 2005).

2.1.3.2 Hedonic

Hedonic is a customer consuming products and services that are primarily based on the desire to get pleasure and happiness (Tifferet and Herstein, 2012). Hedonic reflects the values of experience that include fantasy, impulse, interest, excitement, curiosity, and imaginative. On the other hand, Hedonic values are primarily experience and affective (Kim and Han, 2009). Hedonic values are more subjective and personal than Utilitarian values because Hedonic is the result of feelings of pleasure obtained rather than completion of orientation based on the ratio of benefits and thinking (Holbrook and Batra, 1987).

2.1.4 Physical Environment Quality

Kotler (1973) defines Physical Environment Quality as a spatial design created to create certain effects on customers to increase the likelihood of making a purchase. Bitner (1992) defines it as an objective and physical factor controlled by a restaurant so that it positively influences customer purchasing preferences and decisions. Through the dinescape concept for the physical environment of upscale restaurants where eating is more than just eating out for most customers. Customers might not want to feel at home. They might look for unforgettable experiences and the atmosphere can play an important role in creating unforgettable experiences. To capture how customers perceive Physical Environment Quality in fine dining is dinescape (Ryu and Jang, 2008).

2.1.4.1 Music

Music can be defined as a pleasant voice that influences the conscious and unconscious decisions of the customer (Banat and Wandebori, 2012). (Rea et al., 2010) agree that the listener's mood can be influenced positively or negatively depending on the type of music being played and classical and pop music increases the listener's comfortable feeling and reduces feelings of worry or tension. In addition, Music influences the customer's point of view about waiting times for service in restaurants (Oakes and North, 2006).

2.1.4.2 Staff

According to Ryu and Jang (2008) Staff defines service employees as employees in a restaurant and has a neat appearance and sufficient numbers so it is important to note that employee interactions actually differ from the physical presence of employees. Employee uniforms depict the professional's physical effectively conveying the restaurant's image and core values. Similarly, according to Lam et al. (2001) employees have general characteristics namely, neat, friendly, broad-minded or service-oriented. Baker et al., (1994) revealed that if customers see through the number or appearance of employees, it will positively influence customer emotions.

2.1.4.3 Layout

According to (Arisman, 2010) Layout is a structural form and a pattern in utilizing space planned by arrangement. Layout and location are the placement of machines, equipment and furniture in the physical environment (Ryu and Jang, 2008) and it is very important to create an effective environment to provide comfort for customers by providing space that makes it easy for customers when moving or sitting also comfortable (Nguyen and Leblanc , 2002). In

addition, as a division of sales areas, space used and arrangements (Banat and Wandebori, 2012).

2.1.4.4 Table Settings

Table Settings is to design a table that looks elegant, luxurious and high quality that will attract customers. This is very important in the design of luxury restaurants and influential in creating quality perceptions. Using high quality Table Settings such as glass, porcelain, tableware such as forks, knives and spoons and quality tablecloths (Ryu and Jang, 2008). Tables in restaurants must be arranged in an attractive, durable material, and easy to clean because they provide privacy and intimacy, protect customers from traffic and get hit by customers or other employees (Quinn, 1981) Table settings are important in high-class restaurants, so that settings the table must be designed to present a luxurious image. For example, high-quality cutlery and glass and linen are effective tools. Also, table settings affect customers when they eat at high standard restaurants. This can affect customers cognitively and emotionally (Ryu and Han, 2011).

2.1.4.5 Lighting

Lighting is stimulant lighting in introducing important Physical Environment Quality, especially in the luxury restaurant business and is known to have different effects on customer behavior. For example: it is suitable for businesses that have full services and high prices that offer warm, comfortable and dim lighting (Ryu and Jang, 2008). Dim lighting creates an environment that is familiar to customers Custers et al. (2010) however, Jacquier and Giboreau (2012) show that lighting brightness is important for customers to read menus. Ariffin et al. (2012) found that adequate lighting influences customer impressions.

2.1.4.6 Ambience

The atmosphere includes intangible attributes such as temperature that affect customers unconsciously and Ambience includes aroma and temperature (Ryu and Jang, 2008). The selection of scents must consider the targeted gender to create a pleasant theme, so that customers spend more time and money to buy products and services (Spangenberg et al., 2006). The atmosphere includes temperature settings such as extreme temperatures (very low or very high) creating negative feelings among customers that causes dissatisfaction among customers and as a result, customers spend less time and produce negative words by word of mouth (Lam, 2001). According to Barber et al. (2012) cleanliness in the food sector includes dining rooms, kitchens and small rooms.

2.1.4.7 Aesthetics

Aesthetics or interior design includes colors, furniture, wall hangings, paintings, tables, flowers and designs (Ryu and Jang, 2008). Customers are influenced by Aesthetics in restaurants (Hwang and Ok, 2013) and restaurants use this factor to create the theme of Ryu and Han (2011). Aesthetics can be defined as architectural design, interior design, and decoration which contribute to the Attractiveness of Physical Environment Quality.

2.2 Hypotheses and development of conceptual framework

2.2.1 Effect of Physical Environment Quality on Perceived Value

Seeing the Physical Environment Quality of a place that has never been experienced before by a customer, this can be done by evaluating and expecting quality, luxury, price, service, employees, cleanliness and hygiene and others. Bitner (1992) also believes that Physical

Environment Quality has a direct impact on customers' cognitive responses, such as thinking and perception. The results of the study show the view that Physical Environment Quality significantly influences the perceived value (Durna et al., 2015). Han and Ryu (2009) state that there is a significant relationship between the restaurant's physical environment and perceived value. In addition, the restaurant's physical environment significantly influences the perception of price, decoration and architecture of the restaurant which is very effective in shaping the overall customer perception. From Özdemir and Dinçer (2018) research conducted also shows that Physical Environment Quality refers to the surrounding physical environment when the service delivery process takes place related to the aesthetics, ambience, lighting, table settings, layout, staff and music dimensions and the perceived value dimensions, namely Hedonic and Utilitarian. So based on the research findings above, the following hypothesis is formulated:

- H1: *Aesthetics has a significant effect on Hedonic.*
- H2: *Ambience has a significant effect on Hedonic.*
- H3: *Lighting has a significant effect on Hedonic.*
- H4: *Table Settings has a significant effect on Hedonic.*
- H5: *Layout has a significant effect on Hedonic.*
- H6: *Staff has a significant effect on Hedonic.*
- H7: *Music has a significant effect on Hedonic.*
- H8: *Aesthetics have a significant effect on Utilitarian.*
- H9: *Ambience has a significant effect on Utilitarian.*
- H10: *Lighting has a significant effect on Utilitarian.*
- H11: *Table Settings has a significant effect on Utilitarian.*
- H12: *Layout has a significant effect on Utilitarian.*
- H13: *Staff has a significant effect on Utilitarian.*
- H14: *Music has a significant effect on Utilitarian.*

2.2.2 Effect of Perceived Value on Customer Satisfaction

The relationship between perceived value and customer satisfaction can provide a good service outcome in the food and beverage industry. Patterson and Spreng (1997) emphasized the role of Perceived Value in customer service in the service sector that Perceived Value influences Customer Satisfaction positively and significantly. Ryu et al. (2010) measured the effect of Hedonic and Utilitarian values on customer satisfaction in casual-themed fast food restaurants and found that Utilitarian values had a significant significant effect on customer satisfaction compared to Hedonic values and Hedonic values significantly influenced Customer Satisfaction. So based on the research findings above, the following hypothesis is formulated:

- H15: *Hedonic has a significant effect on Customer Satisfaction.*
- H16: *Utilitarian has a significant effect on Customer Satisfaction.*

2.2.3 Effect of Perceived Value on Customer Loyalty

The relationship between Perceived Value and Customer Loyalty customers can provide a good service in the food and beverage industry. Liu and Jang (2009) studied in the context of Chinese restaurants, perceived value influences the tendency of loyal customer behavior to eat in the future. Ryu et al. (2010) aims to measure the effect of Hedonic and Utilitarian values on the tendency of loyal customer behavior in fast-casual restaurants. As a result, it was

found that the Utilitarian value has a large influence on customer loyalty compared to the Hedonic value and the Hedonic value has a significant effect on Customer Loyalty. So based on the research findings above, the following hypothesis is formulated:

H17: *Hedonic has a significant effect on Customer Loyalty.*

H18: *Utilitarian has a significant effect on Customer Loyalty.*

2.2.4 Effect of Customer Satisfaction on Customer Loyalty

Han and Ryu (2009) state that customer loyalty is given through the physical environment of the restaurant, price perception and customer satisfaction. Weiss et al. (2004) obtained similar results that food quality and physical environment influence satisfaction and satisfaction affects customer loyalty to revisit.

Ryu and Han (2011) state that Customer Satisfaction plays an important role in Customer Loyalty in the fine dining restaurant business. The effect of a significant relationship was found between customer satisfaction and loyalty Jalil et al. (2016). So based on some of the concepts above, hypotheses in this study can be taken, are as follows:

H19: *Customer Satisfaction has a significant effect on Customer Loyalty.*

3. Research Method

3.1 Survey Instrument

Data collection is done by distributing questionnaires to respondents in accordance with the characteristics of the sample that has been described previously, namely by using primary data. Primary data is data obtained directly from respondents' answers through a data collection instrument in the form of a questionnaire that is distributed to respondents with the sample characteristics that have been described. The questionnaire was filled in at the place where the respondent was when the questionnaire was given. After completing the questionnaire, the respondent returns the questionnaire that has been filled out and will then be selected by the researcher. The selected questionnaire is a questionnaire that is completely filled out and according to the filling instructions. After selection, the selected questionnaire will be further processed. The scale used in this study is a Likert Scale, where answers are provided at intervals from strongly disagree to strongly agree. Statements are made using a scale of 1-5 to obtain internal data and are given the following values from 1 = Strongly Disagree, 2 = Disagree, 3 = Neutral, 4 = Agree and 5 = Strongly Agree.

3.2 Research Model

Figure 3.1 Research Model

3.3 Sample

The area used as a place for distributing questionnaires was in the city of Surabaya. Questionnaires are given to male and female in the age range 18-60 years, customers who have visited and done fine dining at least 2 times in the last 6 months and meet the monthly income criteria of between IDR 1,000,000, up to IDR 20,000,000,. Furthermore, data tabulation is performed to recap all respondents' assessment results. After the data is tabulated, then the research model will be tested using AMOS software version 22.0. The questionnaire in this study will be divided into two parts. The first part contains questions to get general information about the respondent that is useful to determine the suitability of the characteristics of the respondent with the sample criteria. The second part contains several statements to obtain research data and analyze the influence between Physical Environment Quality dimensions (aesthetics, ambience, lighting, table settings, layout, Staff and music), Perceived Value (hedonic and utilitarian) dimensions, Customer Satisfaction and Customer

Loyalty. The number of indicators used in this study is 36 indicators, therefore the minimum number of samples needed is 180 - 360 respondents, and for this study a total number of respondents will be determined as 250 respondents. This is due to the complexity of the model which requires more samples. The sample used was 250 respondents, the questionnaire distributed 250 or more questionnaires because not all questionnaires were successfully collected in accordance with what was expected. This process is repeated until the expected number of samples are met. Data collection process started in August 2019 - November 2019. A face to face survey and online form were used in this research.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1 Profile of Respondents

Respondents in this study are customers of the restaurant De Soematra 1910 in Surabaya with the provisions as described above. 280 questionnaires have been distributed and of those 250 questionnaires returned in a complete and workable state. Therefore, all questionnaire data processing will use 250 respondents' data. the majority of the sex of the customers of the De Soematra 1910 restaurant in Surabaya was 54.4% or 136 respondents were women while the remaining 45.6% or 114 respondents were men. So in this study, the majority of respondents who visited and did fine dining at De Soematra 1910 restaurant in Surabaya were women. most of the age of customers from the restaurant De Soematra 1910 in Surabaya as much as 47.6% or 119 respondents were respondents aged 36-50 years. Most of the customer income from the restaurant De Soematra 1910 in Surabaya as much as 61.6% or 154 respondents with income of IDR 10,000,000,. - IDR 15,000,000,. so in this study, the majority of respondents who visited and conducted fine dining at the 1910 De Soematra restaurant in Surabaya were respondents with an income of IDR 10,000,000,. - IDR 15,000,000,.

4.2 Structural Model

The structural model provide a good fit to the data chi-square, significant probability, TLI, and CFI are only marginally accepted. Nevertheless with the fulfillment of RMSEA and CMIN / DF it can be said that this model is fit with the data used in this study. Ferdinand (2002) explains that CMIN / DF is generated from chi-square statistics (CMIN) divided by degree of freedom (DF) which is one indicator to measure the fit level of a model. The results of calculations through confirmatory factor analysis and structural equation models, the model in this study can be accepted, as in Table 4.1 The measurement results have met the criteria for goodness of fit, namely chi-square = 1094,757; significant probability = 0,000; RMSEA = 0.060; CMIN / DF = 1904; TLI = 0.743; and CFI = 0.766. Furthermore, based on this fit model, testing of the 19 hypotheses proposed in this study will be tested, as shown in table 4.1.

Table 4.1 Regression Weights Full Structural Equation Model

			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Std. Estimate	Result
Hedonic	<---	Aesthetics	0.207	0.090	2.308	0.021	0.295	Significant
Utilitarian	<---	Ambience	0.309	0.141	2.197	0.028	0.227	Significant
Utilitarian	<---	Aesthetics	0.048	0.073	0.666	0.505	0.064	Not Significant
Hedonic	<---	Ambience	0.080	0.124	0.647	0.518	0.064	Not Significant
Hedonic	<---	Lighting	0.119	0.059	2.017	0.044	0.184	Significant
Utilitarian	<---	Lighting	0.040	0.062	0.645	0.519	0.057	Not Significant
Hedonic	<---	Table_Settings	0.276	0.116	2.383	0.017	0.301	Significant
Utilitarian	<---	Table_Settings	0.035	0.112	0.308	0.758	0.035	Not Significant
Hedonic	<---	Layout	0.052	0.060	0.862	0.389	0.090	Not Significant
Utilitarian	<---	Layout	0.064	0.060	1.071	0.284	0.104	Not Significant
Hedonic	<---	Staff	0.396	0.175	2.267	0.023	0.304	Significant
Utilitarian	<---	Staff	0.116	0.152	0.763	0.445	0.082	Not Significant
Hedonic	<---	Music	0.098	0.049	2.004	0.045	0.175	Significant
Utilitarian	<---	Music	0.040	0.050	0.806	0.420	0.066	Not Significant
Customer_Satisfaction	<---	Hedonic	0.313	0.085	3.671	***	0.347	Significant
Customer_Satisfaction	<---	Utilitarian	0.404	0.093	4.350	***	0.486	Significant
Customer_Loyalty	<---	Hedonic	0.005	0.153	0.034	0.973	0.003	Not Significant
Customer_Loyalty	<---	Utilitarian	0.204	0.164	1.243	0.214	0.118	Not Significant
Customer_Loyalty	<---	Customer_Satisfaction	1.460	0.332	4.400	***	0.706	Significant

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

5.1 Conclusion

This model was developed in the context of the 1910 De Soematra Restaurant Customer Loyalty research in Surabaya. This research model is formed from the relationship between the dimensions of Physical Environment Quality (Aesthetics, Ambience, Lighting, Table Settings, Layout, Staff and Music) that influence Customer Loyalty through the dimensions of Perceived Value (Hedonic and Utilitarian) and Customer Satisfaction. The formulation of the problem in this research is whether the dimensions of the Physical Environment Quality (Aesthetics, Ambience, Lighting, Table Settings, Layout, Staff and Music) variables have a significant effect on the Perceived Value (Hedonic and Utilitarian) dimensions, the dimensions of the Perceived Value (Hedonic and Utilitarian) variables significant to the Customer Satisfaction and Customer Loyalty variables and the Customer Satisfaction variable has a significant effect on Customer Loyalty. Based on the data processing, the final result is that from 19 hypotheses submitted, 9 hypotheses were accepted and 10 hypotheses were rejected.

5.2 Theoretical Implications

The literature describing the theory of Customer Loyalty has been strengthened by theoretical concepts and empirical support for the factors that influence Customer Loyalty in relation to the 1910 De Soematra restaurant in Surabaya. Some relationships that have a significant effect between variables in previous studies also show the same results in this study so it can be concluded that previous research still has a level of relevance that supports this research in first-class restaurants. Meanwhile, some insignificant relationships between variables in previous studies that showed different or similar results in this study so that it can be concluded the influence of differences in needs, desires, behavior, ways of thinking, ways of thinking and customer culture towards other first class restaurants need another research to support an insignificant influence on this study. Consequently, this study appears to be a new investigation after the first conducted by model builders (Özdemir dan Dinçer, 2018) to confirm the generalization of the model and so, ideas, methods, and findings are correlated to existing literature. By extension, it contributes to the theoretical and managerial aspects of service quality in the upscale or first class restaurant.

5.3 Managerial Implications

Selection in terms of colors, for example, changing soft pastel colors such as a combination of pink and white, white and pastel blue, bluish green and sea blue, light gray and pastel orange, pink and pastel blue, pastel brown and white, pastel yellow and pastel greens and other soft colors that will create an impression of warmth to the customer as well as classy by using 1 or 2 rooms to adjust the thematic desires of the customer (personalization). Maintain the paintings that are owned so that customers do not feel bored so they can rotate the placement of a dominant collection of authentic authentic Dutch history by moving from one room to another. Add a collection of wall ornaments or wall hangings, for example, seasonal events, which are Christmas or New Year, then decorate with Christmas and New Year decorations such as cute dolls, Christmas tree decorations, wallpapers dominated by red or green colors, thick curtains in gold or silver, garland shaped the words "merry Christmas and the new year 2020" and garland various forms of Christmas hats, socks and stars. Maintain discipline with standard operating procedures for service procedures regarding room temperature control such as room temperature ranges from 22°C - 27°C. Training related to operational service standards for waiters or waitresses guarantee cleanliness in accordance with fine dining dining rules from how to serve appetizer menus, main courses to dessert in a sequence and clean where on time in preparing cleanliness (linen, tableware and condiment), replacement or clear plate up, restore the placement of dirty dishes in place according to large or small size, keep the floor clean and ensure there are no broken or dirty plates or glasses so that it becomes more responsive and faster. Furthermore, improving the performance of janitors as well as improving indoor and outdoor room cleanliness by providing good bins and in accordance with classy restaurant standards. The fragrance of roses and jasmine but can be added regularly to the scents such as the fragrance of tulips and lily. Maintaining the quality of chairs and tables in accordance with the quality of materials, functional and attractive color selection according to the thematic room. The dining chair has a shape very similar to the side chair where the surface of the seat is deliberately made flatter, the backrest is higher and upright to maximize comfort while eating. Likewise the dominant round and rectangular dining table made of teak wood to show that the restaurant still impressed the Dutch heritage. Ensure lighting in terms of lighting conditions emitted more warm lights such as yellow and brown colors and combined with the composition of various crystal lamps that

show an elegant impression and place the lights in the corner of the room, on the table or hung. Using tablecloths made of white, patterned, pastel colors or customer personalization based on the thematic room further ensures the completeness, installation and materials used such as molton (under cloth), table cloths and table runners and napkins (cutleries, cups and free) Forms of fold that can be used are pocket, fan, tulip, classic, peacock, snow, ring and others as well as the use of napkins, including environmentally friendly because it can be used repeatedly and does not cost too much.

The dining table arrangement combines Dutch themes and matching colors and for a beautiful appearance laying fresh floral decorations, tissues and candles, dinner arrangements, flower cards, place cards or table cards and pearls to decorate the dining table are important for showing visual luxury and need to pay attention to the layout the location and the number of decorations that are not excessive so as not to fill the table and disturb the customer's space for enjoying fine dining. Tableware and drinking equipment have a heavier quality, generally made of quality silver, fine textured, anti-bacterial, anti-rust and anti-corrosion is considered a luxurious appearance, spoons of this material generally have a more attractive appearance because cutlery with handles that are equipped with engraving and more complete adapted to the food menu served. Equipment located on the table must be clean and look shiny and orderly to show an elegant side and formal impression. The glass used is also made of premium materials and a variety of shapes and functions, for example, the shape of a stemmed glass namely, water goblet as a glass to serve ice water, red wine glass as a glass to serve red wine and champagne glass saucer as a glass to present champagne or ice cream and stemless glass form namely, beer mug as a glass to serve beer, juice glass as a glass to serve juice and high ball glass as a glass to serve soft drinks so that eating and drinking utensils play a role in supporting a more friendly atmosphere, closer and chatter light and quality at the dining table makes customers happy. Arrangement of layout by De Soematra 1910 restaurant in Surabaya by arranging the layout according to the comfortable capacity in one room so that circulation between employees and customers is not disturbed or looks narrow. Adding space or space between the customer's seat and other customers so that customers feel comfortable and appreciated their privacy. Circulation of incoming, outgoing and moving customers between other customers and employees do not collide with each other, obstruct or not interfere with each other (privacy) because it has been carefully planned layout that must be passed by customers and employees with knowledge of training so as not to be hampered circulation during providing services including offering private dining room facilities as rooms occupied by customers that can be reserved specifically for these customers in order to maintain their privacy. Provide training on first-class restaurant service knowledge standards and motivate employees to improve performance in order to achieve the targets and vision and mission of the restaurant De Soematra 1910 in Surabaya which is set so as to get rewards in the form of employee of the month or monthly bonuses. Provide service training ranging from preparation knowledge, presentation from the kitchen to the customer's table and good collaboration with the kitchen is needed. This is important so that customers do not wait too long so that a credo can be made that explains the time required for food to arrive at the customer's table in accordance with specified standards. Periodic training starting from knowledge and service as well as the restaurant De Soematra 1910 in Surabaya with standard operational service procedures for classy restaurants ranging from preparing, serving appetizers to dessert, interacting and communicating with customers. Continue to provide empathy care training regarding caring, respecting and understanding customer feelings so that employees from various positions

when interacting with customers can provide the best service and touch the customer's emotional.

De Soematra 1910 restaurant lighting in Surabaya, which has been applied in every room using dominant yellow and brown lights, giving the impression of warmth to customers who can come with relatives, friends or even lovers. Luxurious designs from De Soematra 1910's restaurant menu list in Surabaya have shown a Dutch vintage design that is the use of white bone composition, restaurant logos and green ornament ornaments and equipped with leather binder which adds to the impression of a first-class restaurant. Customers who wait do not become anxious and depressed if there are soft tones that are good to play such as classical, popular or legendary music such as Mozart, Beethoven, Bach or Chopin or customers can personalize by submitting a request for the song they want to play. The atmosphere that seems romantic or formal then keep the music in a stable low volume (70 decibels) and slow tempo. When soft music is played, visitors eat to enjoy their food and feel comfortable like classical, popular or legendary music such as Mozart, Beethoven, Bach or Chopin. Music is a key element in regulating moods. The harmonization of the selected song is also appropriate namely classical music such as Mozart, Beethoven, Bach and Chopin in the sense of helping to keep the message that customers want to get from the restaurant De Soematra 1910 in Surabaya to remain consistent and support the image of a classy restaurant. music plays an important role in creating personal and personal space around customers, allowing customers to chat and relax without having to feel the presence of other customers. Communication about the image of the restaurant De Soematra 1910 in Surabaya is a classy restaurant with a Dutch nuance through awards or titles such as cultural heritage as "Cultural Heritage" in Surabaya, East Java and rating from well-known online platforms such as traveloka (4.8 from 5 stars) and trip advisor (4.5 of 5), this shows the existence as a classy restaurant that was founded in 1910 until now in 2019. Maintaining various restaurant elements to strengthen the image as a classy restaurant through Aesthetics, Ambience, Lighting, Table Settings, Layout, Staff and Music so as to arouse the enthusiasm of customers while in the restaurant so that customers will feel happy.

Maintaining the level of customer satisfaction through the results of customer satisfaction placed in the corner of the room or the cashier so that customers are more confident by showing the plaque or certificate frame as a classy restaurant that provides the best service so that customer satisfaction is guaranteed. Maintain using international class chefs for example from France so that the quality of food contained on the menu is really delicious and uses the best ingredients and hygienic. Besides that, it can improve by updating the nutritional value once every 3 months and completing the nutritional value in each menu such as energy, fat, vitamins, protein and calories so that the food and drinks served are delicious and healthy for customers of De Soematra 1910 restaurant in Surabaya. Improve by conducting surveys on other classy one restaurants as a study material to regulate the amount of food or drink, starting from considering the portion size, price, plates and glasses used, garnish and arrangement of food and drink on a plate or glass so that restaurants Soematra 1910 in Surabaya. Improving by providing a special corner for customers to fill out an evaluation that is a guest evaluation that contains a survey of food by customers starting shortages, strengths and what menus need to be added so that customers do not feel bored. Communicating the image of the restaurant De Soematra 1910 in Surabaya is a classy restaurant with a Dutch nuance through awards or titles such as cultural heritage as a "Cultural Heritage" in Surabaya, East Java and the rating of well-known online platforms such

as traveloka (4.8 from 5 stars) and trip advisor (4.5 of 5 out of 5) which means food quality from nutritional value, quality ingredients, cooked by international class chefs and hygienic as a classy restaurant serving classy food too. Regular training for employees such as knowledge of serving customers from welcoming arrivals, being able to explain menus, serving food from appetizers to dessert, speed in serving and communicating to customers through empathy care training and implementing standard operating procedures well. Combine the two main elements of food quality and service quality based on the image of a first-class restaurant.

5.4 Limitations and Future Research

Seeing the limitations of the research object that only takes respondents, namely De Soematra 1910 restaurant in Surabaya, it is hoped that subsequent studies using the same or modified models can be applied to different objects to get more general results on the factors that influence Customer Loyalty. Further research is expected to be able to complete the variables that already exist in this research so that it can further enhance understanding of the factors that influence Customer Loyalty, such as attitude, trust, advertising, brand image, word of mouth and product features. Further research can be developed by linking factors that influence Customer Loyalty based on demographic levels. Future research can also broaden the scope of respondents to be studied, or conduct research in areas that are different from current research. So that further research carried out increasingly provides a broad picture of Customer Loyalty. In addition, it is expected to also be able to use the Structural Equational Model (SEM) but by using the Lisrel software in further research.

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